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DELIVERABLE REPORT

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D17.2

Terms of Reference of the Dissemination Plan

Due date

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NEP

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Terms of Reference of the Dissemination Plan

DELIVERABLE DESCRIPTION

The present deliverable regards the Terms of References of the Dissemination Plan (DP) of the NFFA-Europe Pilot project. The DP paves the way on one hand to disseminate the results obtained within the NFFA-Europe Pilot project to the proper target scientific communities and on the other one to reach new scientific communities. This double objective ensures efficiency as well as flexibility through the number of measures considered.

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NATURE

R - Report

DISSEMINATION LEVEL

- P - Public
- PP - Restricted to other programme participants & EC: (Specify)
- RE - Restricted to a group (Specify)
- CO - Confidential, only for members of the consortium

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INTRODUCTION

The NFFA-Europe Pilot is a Research Infrastructure project financed by the EU offering harmonised, interoperable and integrated services in the field of the European nanoscience research. European and non-European scientists can submit applications to access the offered instruments and become NFFA-Europe Pilot users. The Dissemination Plan (DP) of the NFFA-Europe Pilot project has an interconnected two-fold objective. The outputs and results developed within the project will be, on one hand, disseminated to proper target scientific communities and, on the other one, used to attract new potential users. The NFFA-Europe Pilot DP is based upon the project strategy outlined in the WP17 of the Annex 1 of NFFA-Europe Pilot Grant Agreement (GA), where the actions to disseminate the generated foreground represent the best available option according to the available budget. The present DP describes in detail the tasks and sets the rules for their implementation. To this respect, the WP17 Board is defined by the 4 task leaders present in the WP, and it is chaired by the WP Leader.

The present plan is approved by the WP17 Board and will be forwarded to the management of the NFFA-Europe Pilot. It will be subjected to regular improvement throughout the project lifetime, according to the collected experiences.

DISSEMINATION PLAN

The disseminating activities of the NFFA-Europe Pilot DP are based upon the best practices already in use in other similar projects and in line with the EC guidelines. The dissemination strategy of the present project is based upon the identification of the subjects, of the targets and of the means, and shall be supported by a timely and efficient management.

The DP and its measures are described in the Task 17.2 – Dissemination of the Annex 1, part A of NFFA-Europe Pilot GA. The DP is intimately linked to the task 17.1 – Communication - and the, Communication Plan, as some communication actions are the vehicle to disseminate and exploit the results originated within the project. Regular meetings between the task leaders of the tasks 17.1 and 17.2 will take place for an efficient synchronization of the two plans. Moreover, regular meetings of the WP17 Board will take place to tune the management of the WP17 according to the evolution of the findings.

HIGHLIGHTS PROPOSALS

The proposals submitted by the users show indeed the trend of the scientific communities and they can be ranked according to the scientific and technology interest. Highlight proposals stand out for their excellent, promising and challenging proposed research, and will represent the flagship of the project proposals. Synergies with the Joint Activities (JA) will be investigated according to the selected highlights proposals; in particular, to the WP11-15 for research topics, to the WP16 for the FAIR data approach and to the WP18 for industrial users.

Target: the project user community.

CRITERIA

During the proposal assessment, at each call the ARP identifies outstanding proposals on hot scientific and technological topics, if any. The decision of the ARP on the highlight proposals may not be appealed. These proposals will be marked as *highlight proposal*. The selection criteria are listed below in order of priority:

- Excellent, promising and challenging proposed research
- Hot scientific and technological topics
- Comprehensive approach: well-justified and balanced access to complementary techniques/methods.

In order to select a highlight proposal, a large consensus among the evaluators shall be reached.

AWARD

Highlight proposals will be awarded:

- Priority access: the instrument scientists will give best possible priority for scheduling the experiments of highlight proposals.
- Name and ID as news on our website
- Special focus on outcomes. If the access is successful, invitation at one NFFA-Europe Pilot workshop to present the results. If the event will take place live, travel costs will be covered by the project. If the access is successful, the proposal will be evaluated for a possible Press Release.

SUCCESS STORIES

Highlight proposals will be followed during the project lifetime. As soon as successful scientific results of highlight proposals will be made disclosed by the users, they will be invited to present their research outcomes at NFFA-Europe Pilot dissemination events and, moreover, will be included in the periodic project Newsletters and suggested for the special section on project results in the dashboard of the Funding&Tender EU portal.

DISSEMINATION EVENT

The NFFA-Europe Pilot organizes activities to exploit the foreground developed during the project, with the parallel goal to increase the awareness of the scientific communities. This action includes three different types of meetings, as described below. However, the three dissemination events defined here will not limit the WP17 Board to advertise the NFFA-Europe Pilot project at any other conference that is found to be functional to the project with the double goal to disseminate the foreground developed during the project and to attract new users.

Target: the scientific communities and potential user.

EMRS MEETINGS

In the NFFA-Europe Pilot Grant Agreement, the European Materials Research Society EMRS has been included as a sub-contractor for the participation to its meetings. The subcontract includes:

- 10 min pre-recorded presentation + Questions/Answers at 3 ONLINE conferences
- Organisation of 2 one-day NFFA topical workshop at 2 different EMRS conferences with an estimated attendance of 100 participation:
 - o renting rooms and technical tools
 - o renting poster boards (two-sided use) for poster sessions
 - o 2 lunches for the participants
 - o 2 coffee breaks (morning/afternoon)
- Renting of exhibition spaces at 2 different EMRS conferences: 2 booths.
- Renting of VIRTUAL exhibition booth at EMRS 2021 conference

IMPLEMENTATION AND SCHEDULE

The EMRS runs two meetings per year, the Spring one in May-June and the Fall one in September.

Two topical workshops for about 100 persons each are foreseen, and in particular the 1st Topical Workshop focuses on lithography and nano-patterning, and it will be chaired by Yasin Ekinci (PSI), while the topic of the second one will be chosen by the WP17 board, according to the users' activity.

The two Topical Workshops were supposed to be organized in the EMRS Spring meeting 2022 and in the Spring meeting 2023, when the first results obtained during the project become available.

Unfortunately, the current pandemic has altered all initial plans that need to be updated only when the situation due to the pandemic will improve. For this reason, participation to virtual conference has been also considered where a pre-recorded registration with Q&A sessions will be used at three EMRS Virtual Meetings, likely at the first three events, i.e. Spring and Fall Meeting 2021 and the Spring Meeting 2022.

The Virtual Exhibition booth will be present at the Fall Meeting 2021.

In case that not all the allocated budget will be used for the EMRS meetings, it may be allocated to other 17.2.2 sub-subtasks, by following the EU rules for the unspent subcontract budget.

ON-DEMAND WORKSHOPS

During the lifetime of the project on-demand workshops will be organized. These on-demand workshops have no pre-defined topics, but they will be selected on the basis of the scientific interests shown by the user communities as well as by the project partners. In principle, the on-demand workshops are supposed to be in connection to the General Assembly (GeAs), especially in the case that physical meetings will be possible. However, as the GeAs meetings may take place at middle way and at the end of the project, the on-demand workshops may also be disregarded from the GeAs meetings, especially in the case of virtual events.

DECISION ON TOPICS

Topics will be proposed by the members of the WP17 Board and also users and scientific beneficiary staff can be contacted to propose topics. Decision is taken by the WP17 Board with single majority, after consulting also the NFFA-Europe Pilot management and keeping in mind the needs of the whole project, by investigating on the proposal and experiment topics as well as the webinar ones. In case of a tie, the Chair has the casting vote. Cross-disciplinary topics are considered as an added value for the selection.

FINANCIAL CONTRIBUTION

The WP17 will distribute a financial contribution up to 10.000 € or 50% of the total event cost, whichever is the lowest, to 1 dissemination event per year organized by the NFFA-Europe Pilot beneficiaries. The call for application will be launched by email and will be advertised on the project web portal. The NFFA-Europe Pilot project shall fulfil the EU rules on these events, covering organizational costs only, and not providing a sponsorship to the event. The NFFA-Europe Pilot contribution will be paid after the event upon receiving a detailed financial report with copies of all the invoices paid. Unspent budget on this sub-subtask will be automatically redistributed to the other sub-subtasks of the 17.2.2 after the payment of the financial contribution of the successful application.

Target: the scientific communities and potential user.

CRITERIA

The following selection criteria, listed in alphabetic order, will be used to select the successful application:

- Cross-disciplinarity
- Excellent and hot scientific topics
- Grand challenge
- Impact
- Size of the event
- Size of the interested user community within the project

Applications for events where the project beneficiary is not the main organizer, but a co-organizer, are eligible but they will be given a lower priority.

APPLICATION RULES

Applications must be submitted within the defined deadline and can be submitted for events that will take place within 12 months from the application deadline, unless described otherwise in the call for applications. Applications for events that already took place are not eligible and will be removed from the selection process. The application shall contain:

- an exhaustive description of the planned event
- the name of invited (confirmed and foreseen) speakers
- a detailed budget of the event

A template will be made available for the application. The applications will be submitted by email to the WP17 Leader by one of the project beneficiaries.

SELECTION PANEL

The WP17 Board will decide upon the topics of the on-demands workshops per written procedure or per videoconference. In case of a tie, the Chair has the casting vote. A decision is expected not later than 4 weeks after the submission deadline.

ACADEMIC DISSEMINATION

The NFFA-Europe Pilot project will be present at academic events that are strategically important for the project with a double objective: on one side to disseminate the foreground developed during the lifetime of the project and, on the other side, the opportunities offered by the project with the ultimate goal to attract new users. Participation to dissemination events will be considered according to the available budget.

The WP17 Board will decide on the Conference to visit at the beginning of each year. A list of priority events will be defined not later than February each year. For the 2021, the following events are under investigation:

- EuroNanoForum 2021, 5-6 May 2021, virtual conference, we plan to have a NFFA-Europe Pilot booth - <https://euronanoforum2021.eu> and the project will be present at the satellite meeting Research and Technology Infrastructures for the European Nanotechnology Ecosystem, 4 May 2021.
- 17th International Conference on Advanced NanoMaterials, 22-24.07.2021 Aveiro, Portugal
- SPIE Conferences - <https://www.advanced-nanomaterials-conference.com>
- Nano 2021 Virtual Conference, 15-16 June 2021, virtual conference - <https://conference.tappinano.org>
- Micro and Nano Engineering Conference, 20-23 September 2021, Turin, Italy - <https://www.mne2021.org>
- NanoTexnology, 3-10 July 2021, Thessaloniki, Greece - <https://www.nanotexnology.com>
- International Conference on Research Infrastructures (ICRI), June 1-3 2021, <http://icri2021.ca>
- Trends in Nanotechnology International Conference (TNT2021), October 04-08, TIRANA, ALBANIA, <http://www.tntconf.org/2021/index.php?conf=21>

The list above should not be considered exhaustive and additional events can be considered.

One of the selection criteria of the dissemination events is an underrepresented user community within the project.

CONCLUSIONS

The present DP of the NFFA-Europe Pilot project contains measures that will contribute to disseminate the foreground developed during the project as well as increase the visibility of the NFFA-Europe Pilot project to attract new user communities.

The present DP will be monitored and cross matched towards the Communication Plan in order to find synergies and avoid duplications. Moreover, the actions described here may be revised to improve its efficiency.

LIST OF ACRONYMS

Acronym	Description
ARP	Access Review Panel
DP	Dissemination Plan
EMRS	European Materials Research Society
GA	Grant Agreement
GeAs	General Assembly
NFFA	Nano Foundry and Fine Analysis
ToR	Terms of Reference
WP	Work Package

